

InGRID

Supporting expertise in inclusive growth

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Deliverable 6.1

PROCEEDINGS

Data Forum 1 Census Data

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1 . Data Forum on Harmonization and Uses of European Microdata

1.1 Where and when?

Type of event	Data Forum	Organising partner(s)	CED
Date	18-19 January 2018	Main responsible partner	CED
Location/venue	Hotel 'H10 Casanova'	Date call launched	On invitation
City	Barcelona	Deadline for applications	On invitation
Country	Spain	N° applicants	On invitation
Number of days	Two and one night	N° participants	38
Milestone/deliverable	N°MS 63	N° speakers	22

1.1.1 General information

The Data Forum brought together representatives from European Statistical Institutes, agencies and researchers with strong experience in cross-national comparative data to discuss innovation and solutions to integrate Labour Force Survey microdata for the study of poverty, work, and living conditions. The Data Forum consisted of six sessions of three or four presentations each, alternating between sessions of data users and data producers.

1.1.2 Major goal of event

The *Data Forum on Harmonization and Uses of European Microdata* proposes to harmonize Labour Force Surveys of cooperating European National Statistics Offices in a global, scientific use, extract management system.

Three modus operandi for entrusting Labour Force Surveys into the global project will be considered at the meeting:

1. Eurostat versions of the surveys from the member state statistical office
2. National versions directly from the member state statistical office
3. Eurostat versions from Eurostat instructed by the corresponding member state statistical office

This initiative aims to complement the conventional, whole-file dissemination with a twenty-first century system offering:

1. Open access interactive metadata;
2. Restricted access harmonized microdata via be-spoke, pooled extracts—for selected countries, years, variables, and even subpopulations—tailored precisely to the needs of each individual researcher or research team.

IPUMS/CED extends the highly successfully Census Microdata Series, currently encompassing 85 countries, with a world-wide Labour Force/Household Series piloted for 3 countries: India, Nigeria, and the USA.

We expect to create regional labour force data collections for other world regions using IPUMS principles, which would make it easy for researchers to do truly world-spanning research. From the start, European researchers may take advantage of the IPUMS-CPS database that harmonizes the U.S. employment survey. We could add variables to make those data even more easily interoperable with the European collection.

1.1.3 The event within the InGRID-2 project

The data forums are organised answering Task 1 in Work Package 6 of the InGRID-2 project. The events are meant as a meeting place for data providers, research-users and stakeholders to discuss the challenges of the particular data type and to discuss suitable actions for addressing these challenges. Topics of the data forums are data on household finances, census data, the WageIndicator websurvey data, and national working conditions surveys. For every topic, two times during the project specific data forums will be organised.

The Barcelona *Data Forum on Harmonization and Uses of European Microdata* has served to create a network of data producers and main data users from international leading organization (e.g. OECD, Eurostat, ILO, World Bank). The future availability of harmonized LFS data to the research community will be a major break-through in the next years.

The initial focus area of the data forum was the integration and harmonization of census microdata. However, the organization decided to include EU-LFS in the discussion because several tasks in different InGRID's work packages will use this microdata. This is the case of Task 5 in WP9 where is expected to use EU-LFS for exploring regional poverty and inequality dynamics in small areas. Task 3 in WP10 will also work with EU-LFS for creating indicators to understand the influence of demographic factors on unemployment, poverty and material deprivation. EU-LFS will also be the main data source in WP11 for harmonizing and integrating data on vulnerable groups and on working conditions and employment relations.

The data forum allowed to put in contact IPUMS/IECM with some national statistical institutes and international organizations and to explore their possibilities of future collaborations.

1.2 Who and what?

1.2.1 Curriculum/programme: detailed information on structure and content of curriculum/programme of the event

The data forum consisted of six sessions of three or four presentations each, alternating between sessions of data users and data producers.

The final version of the programme is available on the project website:

<http://www.inclusivegrowth.eu/data-forums/data-forum---ced---18-19-january-2018>

1.2.1.1 Short description of each session

In the first session, representatives from CED, InGRID and IPUMS presented the objectives of the data forum and their organizations. Each presentation consisted in 15-20 minutes followed by questions by the other participants.

This was followed by sessions by researchers from universities and international organizations. They presented their approaches for harmonizing and processing LFS and studies using LFS from a crossnational perspective.

There were two presentations by national statistical institutes' representatives. They presented their experiences collecting censuses and LFS data and the particularities of data collection and dissemination for each country.

All presentations are available on the project website: <http://www.inclusivegrowth.eu/data-forums/data-forum---ced---18-19-january-2018>

1.2.1.2 Short bio lectures/speakers

The data forum was organised by the Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED) and actively supported by IPUMS and the participants of the Data Forum were representatives from European statistical institutes, agencies (Eurostat, OECD, ILO, Eurofound, World Bank) and researchers with strong experience in the use of Labour Force Surveys to discuss innovation and solutions to integrate labour force survey microdata for the study of poverty, work, and living conditions.

The researchers and agencies were invited to present and discuss their methodologies for LFS and the challenges and the possibilities for crossnational research based on this European microdata and the possibility of integrate the EU-LFS in a RI. Representatives of the national statistical offices offered an update about their protocols and procedures on LFS, in particular, about the preparation of a scientific use microdata and how to entrust LFS and census microdata into IEPM/IPUMS, a social sciences research infrastructure. The representatives of IPUMS approached the harmonization of EU microdata.

Find a complete list of participants in the event, including their institution affiliation, at the end of this document.

1.2.1.3 Short report on the event

The *Data Forum on Harmonization and Uses of European Microdata* took place in the city of Barcelona from 17 to 19 of January. It was organized by the Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED) in collaboration with IPUMS (University of Minnesota). The data forum was funded by the InGRID-2 project, *Supporting research infrastructures for European expertise on inclusive growth from data to policy*, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (Grant Agreement no. 730998).

The data forum brought together representatives from European statistical institutes, agencies and researchers with strong experience in cross-national comparative data to discuss innovation and solutions to integrate Labour Force Survey microdata for the study of poverty, work, and living conditions.

38 people attended the data forum, including 13 representatives from the national statistical offices, 6 delegates from the agencies, 8 researchers, the director and the 3 higher people in charge of IPUMS, the InGRID project manager, the director and 5 researchers from the organizing institution (CED), and 2 staff people.

There were 22 presentations in 6 sessions. In the first session, we presented the InGRID-2 project to the participants and the specific goals of the event. We also presented the IPUMS research infrastructure and the work done harmonizing and disseminating microdata. The researchers and the delegates from the agencies had the leading role in the second, fourth and fifth sessions. These sessions were focused on the cross-national research based on European microdata. The third and sixth sessions consisted of presentations by representatives of the national statistical offices about their national LFS and the entrusting of LFS microdata into IEPM/IPUMS.

During the meeting some social activities took place. Researches were invited to share their experiences with other participants through social activities like coffee breaks, two lunches and two social dinners. In addition, two guided city tours with the group of participants were organized: a stroll around the old town centre.

1.2.2 Conclusions/next steps

The workshop gathered 38 persons from 25 different institutions, including representatives from national statistical offices and international agencies. The main conclusions:

- There is an increased recognition of the value of having international data in harmonized and open access form.
- The IPUMS international approach is considered as a best-practice in terms of data preservation, harmonization and dissemination.
- The possibility of having an harmonized set of European Labour Force Survey microdata was well received by all members represented in the area
- Several European countries have already given the authorization to launch the harmonization of EU – LFS microdata (examples: Spain, Austria, United Kingdom, Greece, France, Canada, United States).
- The IPUMS team (based at the Minnesota Population Center) will seek possibilities of funding the harmonization of global LFS data, including the European. A grant proposal is expected to be submitted by the fall.
- Future steps:
 - CED will collaborate with IPUMS in confirming and increasing the number of participating countries in the future LFS harmonization.
 - A proposal will likely be submitted by the fall. Future work will be conditioned to the success of this grant. International agencies with expertise in LFS will be contacted to seek their support or endorsement of the new proposal.

1.3 Quality and evaluation

1.3.1 Dissemination activities

Each event announcement is made available on the InGRID-2 website, where links to the programme, financial and practical information for participants, ... are also provided. Further each event is added to the (monthly) InGRID-2 newsflash, which is disseminated out to a broad mailinglist. When a newsletter is made at the time of the call, the call is also included in the newsletter.

In addition, the call is made available to the following other channels:

- the Center for Demographic Studies website
- the Center for Demographic Studies Newsletter

1.3.2 Selection criteria and procedure (participants)

1.3.2.1 On invitation

Participation to the event on invitation.

1.3.2.2 Additional procedure, requirements to participate and selection criteria

Participants in the data forum were selected based on their strong experience in the use of EU-LFS microdata from a crossnational perspective.

Representatives from national statistical institutes were responsible or members of the departments of the LFS at a national level.

1.3.3 Event organisation

The data forum was organised by the Centre d'Estudis Demogràfics (CED). The location of the workshop was at H10 Casanova, Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes 559, 08011 Barcelona, Spain. (<https://www.h10hotels.com/es/hoteles-barcelona/h10-casanova>)

Albert Esteve was the main organiser. The administrative and technical staff was composed by Teresa Antònia Cusidó and Joan García.

1.3.4 Comments/evaluation of the event by the participants

No form has been made, nevertheless lots of participants sent us emails thanking us for the invitation at the meeting and some national statistical offices added that they consider it a very interesting conference for entrusting and harmonizing the LFS data into the IPUMS research infrastructure, so they ask what the next steps would be to progress in this issue. From Eurostat we were suggested to participate in the meetings that they hold twice a year with the persons in charge of EU-LFS.

1.4 Additional remarks

None.

InGRID-2

Integrating Research Infrastructure for European expertise on Inclusive Growth from data to policy

Referring to the increasingly challenging EU2020-ambitions of Inclusive Growth, the objectives of the InGRID-2 project are to advance the integration and innovation of distributed social sciences research infrastructures (RI) on ‘poverty, living conditions and social policies’ as well as on ‘working conditions, vulnerability and labour policies’. InGRID-2 will extend transnational on-site and virtual access, organise mutual learning and discussions of innovations, and improve data services and facilities of comparative research. The focus areas are (a) integrated and harmonised data, (b) links between policy and practice, and (c) indicator-building tools.

Lead users are social scientist involved in comparative research to provide new evidence for European policy innovations. Key science actors and their stakeholders are coupled in the consortium to provide expert services to users of comparative research infrastructures by investing in collaborative efforts to better integrate micro-data, identify new ways of collecting data, establish and improve harmonised classification tools, extend available policy databases, optimise statistical quality, and set-up microsimulation environments and indicator-building tools as important means of valorisation. Helping scientists to enhance their expertise from data to policy is the advanced mission of InGRID-2. A new research portal will be the gateway to this European science infrastructure.

This project is supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730998.

More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.eu